

Semantic Data Modeling for the Census Database **Deliverable 7 - Setup of Repository**

Deliverable 7 is the main outcome of WP6 (Repository Setup). It aimed to ensure the accessibility of the generated semantic research data as open data. Its purpose is to produce, as a minimal viable product, a space for accessing and downloading the semantic data within the context and the timeframe of the project in a way that will allow researchers to make use of the semantic output for their own research ends. For the context of the project itself, a triple store was set up for testing and manipulating the produced RDF collaboratively with the Census project team. We have established a SparQL endpoint employing [Apache Jena Fuseki 4.5.0](#) on a remote server. The Census triple store then can be accessed and queried [here](#). A [list](#) of basic SparQL queries has been created to help the researcher to develop more complex research agendas. The long-term triple store using the same repository will be installed locally by members of the HU to serve as a SparQL endpoint after the end of the project.

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